

Association Between Food Label Reading Habits and Knowledge, Attitude and Practices in Young Adults

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Abstract

The study investigates the association between food label reading habits and knowledge, attitude, and practices in young adults along with key barriers hindering the use of food label. A cross-sectional study was conducted among 202 adults aged 18-30 years of urban and sub-urban areas of Hyderabad and Secunderabad. Data was collected using a structured pre evaluated questionnaire, nutrition knowledge, label reading practices, attitudes of consumers, barriers and awareness. The analysis revealed, 90% of young adults read food labels, indicating a pattern of frequent but superficial engagement. ANOVA and post-hoc analysis revealed that factors like age significantly influenced attention to specific nutrients, older adults focused on nutrients like saturated fat, cholesterol and protein. Attitude were positive across age group with 68% acknowledging that labels influence their purchasing decisions. However, practices revealed short time spend on labels with several strong correlated ($r=0.637$, $p<0.001$) barriers including small font size, complex labels and distrust in label information. Analysis confirmed that these barriers collectively hindered effective label understanding and usage. And finally positive labels engagement significantly impacted awareness ($p<0.001$) and dietary practices ($p=0.005$) in young adults. The finding emphasizes for early label education with easy to interpret and trustworthy labels to bridge the gap between awareness and application. further enhancing label literacy, improving dietary decision making and policy advocacy. Future longitudinal study is needed to test whether improved literacy and affordability translates into sustained immediate dietary change.

Key Words: Food label reading, Young adults, Nutrition literacy, Attitudes and practices, Perceived barriers

Introduction

"To eat is a necessity, but to eat intelligently is an art" (François de La Rochefoucauld). In today's fast-moving world where convenience has overshadowed conscious choice with massive urbanization, prolonged work hours leading to surge in consumption of ready to eat prepackaged food, the simple act of eating food has evolved into a complex decision-making process. Where often the nutritional foods are avoided and replaced with the convenient once [1]. Food labels are the first detailed tool seen by the customers during shopping, and displays information such as ingredients, nutritive value, shelf life and the presence of allergens of the selected product. However, food labelling also represents a marketing tool influencing perception of the food quality and directly the dietary choice of consumers. [15]

Food labels globally, are being recognized as a public health necessity, with the World Health Organization (WHO) advocating for standardized, evidence-based labels to combat non-communicable diseases (NCDs) [14]. Though FSSAI has mandated nutrient labelling and list of ingredients on packaged or prepackaged foods and launched initiatives like 'Eat right India' the actual consumer engagement with food labelling still remains low, with only 22% of Indian consumers reported reading labels as per [9]. A per the Lancet GBD study (2024) Metabolic syndrome also called the non-communicable diseases are now the leading cause of early death and disease related disabilities in young adults world-wide. Effective labelling can curb obesity trends by

empowering consumers to reject unhealthy packaged foods, yet its potential remains underutilized in India's evolving food landscape. This underscores the urgent need to evaluate their dietary reliance on processed foods and engagement with food labels ^[16] ^[13].

Use of food labels usually depends on consumers ability to understand, interpret, and implement in real life, where the actually gap excites ^[17]. Identifying gaps in young consumer behaviour through Knowledge, Attitudes, and Practices (KAP) is important for knowing their level of awareness, enforcing efficient guidelines and encouraging healthy eating habit in young adults. ^[7]. This study addresses these risks by examining food label reading behaviour through the lens of Knowledge, Attitude, and Practices (KAP) — and identifying the barriers that may limit their effectiveness among young consumers.

Objectives of the study

1. Assess the knowledge young adults in terms of nutritional information and its influencing factors
2. Examine the attitudes young adults hold towards the importance of food labels.
3. Evaluate the label-reading practices of young adults, including frequency, perceived barriers and its impact reading on dietary practices and awareness.

Review Of Literature

Findings have shown how an increasing content in literature underlines the importance of nutrition literacy in improving the interaction of consumers with food labelling. According to Perumal et al. (2022), consumers turn to nutrition labelling to obtain health-related information, and the most well-known ingredients that they pay attention to are fat, sugar, and sodium as they are difficult to decipher. In response, the FDA updated the food labelling laws in 2021 to increase transparency ^[2]. In a similar manner, Shireen et al. (2022) and Shah et al. (2024) identified that even consumers who possess higher levels of nutrition knowledge are less likely to resort to food labels, the factors that prevent them are the complexity and inconsistencies in this terminology ^[3], ^[4]. Other studies also report the preference of standardization of information per 100g rather than per serving which could enhance understanding. Using labels is dependent on demographic factors including age, education, and career. According to Dwivedi et al. (2022), young adults were more accustomed to health claims, the health care students also found it important to have labelling on foods but most said they used it less due to time crunches or unappealing label construction. It was recommended that educational programs should also be conducted to promote the high consumption of labels among future health professionals ^[5]. Liao and Yang (2023) further established that nutrition knowledge indirectly influences label usage via attitude but to their surprise label trust was negatively associated with label usage, which may be due to baseless trust or not doing critical evaluation on the nature of labels ^[6].

It is also critically important that sociocultural context should be considered. According to the work by Jiang et al. (2024), urban and educated adolescents had more positive nutrition knowledge and eating attitude than their rural and less educated counterparts ^[7]. However, a study by Rafiya and Jayakaran (2024) among the adolescent girls showed that attitudes were more strong predictors of label use than knowledge ^[8]. These were repeated in health students by Veena Suresh and others (2024) who look at health students who expressed positive attitudes but had no practice and knowledge ^[9]. It was found that women, urban residents, and educated people with a university education appeared to have an increased label use (Ljubičić et al., 2022) ^[10]. Resultantly, Paliwal et al. (2025) discovered education and age as weak predictors, but nonetheless, statistically significant. The use of labels is minimized in low- and middle-income conditions ^[11]. Ambak et al. (2018) recorded the fact that 55 percent of Malaysian adults had never looked at food labels, and the majority of them went by the expiration dates ^[12]. Lastly, Kansal et al. (2023) emphasized that Indian teens did not hesitate to eat unenjoyable packaged foods and that it was complicated to interpret labels that were not written in their native dialect. This evidence necessitates the need to have less complicated label designs as well as specific education that would improve the use of labels by different populations ^[13].

Methodology

A cross-sectional study was conducted among 202 young adults aged 18-30 years selected through convenience sampling technique. Data was collected using a structured questionnaire (pre-tested) which includes demographic details, food choices & preferences, nutrition knowledge using a Likert scale, label reading practices, attitudes of consumers, barriers and awareness, their answers were analysed by using the IBM SPSS software version 28.0 and Microsoft Excel. Descriptive statistics (mean, median, mode) for frequency of food label reading and Inferential statistics such as ANOVA, LSD post-hoc analysis for attitude and impact of label reading, and Spearman's Rank Correlation for barriers in understanding labels, were applied accordingly to summarise the data and to determine group-based differences and relationships between key variables.

Result and Discussion

The findings are organised under three important domains as per the objective's knowledge, attitude and practices. Starting with demographics, out of 202 participants majority falls under the age group of 18-27 years and more than half of them had graduate education. More respondents possessed normal BMI (71.3%) which implies a rather healthy population. Coming to shopping frequency of the participants - 37.1% shopped month and 40.7% shopped weekly whereas the rest shopped on a daily basis and the (Figure-1) top 3 influencing factors are - the price (91.6%), taste and shelf life.

Figure 1: Distribution of Respondents Based on Factors Influencing Food Purchasing Decisions (N = 202)

1. Knowledge:

Even though most 90% of the young adults said they read food labels, it depends on their knowledge in ascertaining the degree to which they understand. (Table 1) Participants in all groups had the capability to recognize food components of the major labels, yet there is no significant difference between the groups in their capability to interpret and use label information effectively ($F = 0.097$, $p = 0.962$), indicating that there is a lack of nutritional literacy despite frequent exposure.

ANOVA, followed LSD post-hoc analysis (Table 2) revealed that age significantly influenced attention to certain label components, with participants aged 21–23 years old were more conscious of saturated fat, cholesterol, carbohydrates, and serving size, while older participants 27–30 years were more attentive to protein. Indicating a development of pattern for label awareness and nutrition concern with increasing or progressing age, backing statement as age increase label reading habit also increases. Suggesting for targeted label education.

Table 1: Understanding and use of food label information

Variable Compared	F	Sig.	Interpretation
Can understand and use food label information.	.097	.962	This implies while young adults recognize the importance of labels, their ability to interpret and use them effectively varies or requires further improvement.

Table 2: Age with different factors influencing food label interpretation and reading behaviour.

Factor	Age-wise Significant Differences	(p-value)	Interpretation
Serving Size	21–23 vs 27–30	.040	Older adults pay more attention to serving size than younger ones
Saturated Fat	18–20 vs 21–23; 21–23 vs 27–30	.019 .012	21–23 age group is more aware of saturated fat
Cholesterol	18–20 vs 21–23	.026	21–23-year-olds consider cholesterol more than teens
Carbohydrates	18–20 vs 21–23	.013	21–23 age group shows higher interest in carbs
Protein	21–23 vs 27–30	.043	Older group (27–30) likely prioritizes protein more
Sugar	21–23 vs 27–30	.043	27–30 age group pays less attention to sugar than 21–23

2. Attitude

Table 3: Attitude young adults toward food label importance

Variable Compared	F	Sig.	Interpretation
Nutritional labels for healthy choices	4.084	.008	Participants actively consider label information while selecting food products for better health.
Reading labels is important before buying.	3.241	.023	Participants support the statement which reflects a positive attitude toward label awareness in decision-making.

Figure 2: Does any of the mentioned statement [attitude] affect your purchasing decisions (N = 202)

From table 3 - young adults consider nutritional labels as important for making healthy food choices ($F = 4.084, P = .008$) and referring before purchasing ($F = 3.241, P = .023$), indicating they actively consider label information for better health and reflects a positive attitude toward label awareness in decision-making. Further (figure 2), majority of the respondents, 68% felt their attitudes towards food labels does influence their purchasing decisions, while 32 percent, reported otherwise which indicates a overall positive towards label reading though they may lack awareness or confidence or trust in them highlighting potential gaps.

3. Practice

Frequency and duration of label reading - Time spent on labels (figure 3) demonstrated, 32.7 % spend 30-60 second and 27.2% spend 10-30 second reading labels. Whereas about 20.3% spent >1 minute, while 8.4% did not read labels. Indicating, while a majority of participants engage with food labels briefly, a small proportion of them either do not read them or spend minimal time in reading, revealing a gap between exposure and in-depth use and suggesting a need to promote better label awareness and interpretation skills

Perceived barriers to food label usage are multifaceted. Spearman’s correlation analysis (Table 4) revealed that the barriers were significantly associated ($p < .001$) with one another and collectively impacted label use. The problems of design and trust-issues are widespread across demographic groups or uniformly experienced across age groups. Hence, confirming these barriers as hinderance to understanding and practices of label reading.

Figure 3: Average Time Spent on Reading Food Labels by Respondents (N = 202)

Table 4: To analyse barriers and challenges young adults face in understanding and using food labels using Correlations - Spearman's rho

Primary Barrier	Strongly Correlated With (ρ , p-value)	Interpretation
Font too small	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hard to understand terms ($\rho=.321$, $p<.01$) • Unsure how to use labels ($\rho=.425$, $p<.01$) 	Practice is negatively amplified by poor readability of design and understanding.
Healthy food expensive	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Distrust in information ($\rho=.133$, ns) • Unsure how to use labels ($\rho=.362$, $p<.01$) 	The issue of cost leads limited understanding and practice.
Distrust in labels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Small fonts ($\rho=.303$, $p<.01$) • Hard to understand terms ($\rho=.249$, $p<.01$) 	Scepticism can come through design and complexity.
Time-consuming	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Label complexity ($\rho=.379$, $p<.01$) • High cost ($\rho=.175$, $p<.05$) 	Labels difficult to interpret lead to consuming more time and affordability

Notes: ρ = Spearman's correlation coefficient; significant ($p < .05$); ns = not significant ($p = \geq .05$)

Table 5: Impact of positive practice on dietary habit and awareness LSD-Post hoc analysis

Category	Comparison	p-value
Label advocacy	1 vs 3	.027*
	1 vs 4	.022*
Dietary influence	1 vs 3	.005**
	1 vs 4	.004**
	1 vs 5	<.001***
Policy support	1 vs 2	.020*
	2 vs 5	.026*
Label preferences	1 vs 4	.002**
	2 vs 4	.017*

Note: Only selected statistically significant comparisons are shown ($p<.05$, ** $p<.01$, *** $p<.001$).

Finally, the impact of label reading practice on dietary habits ($p = .005$) and awareness interventions ($P = .027$) were found to significantly influence participant's knowledge and behaviours related to food label use. Participants who spent more time reading labels were more likely to encourage others to read them ($p < 0.001$) favour clearer labelling policy ($p = .039$) and suggest improvements with constructive feedbacks ($p = .016$) such as adding larger font and/or simpler wording or language. This highlights that even short engagement with labels positively influences dietary practices on a long term and public health awareness.

Conclusion:

This study concludes a significant association between food label reading habits and young adults' knowledge, attitudes, and practices (KPA). While most young adults check labels frequently, their understanding and interpretation were often limited, pointing to a gap that lies between awareness and actual knowledge they hold. Barriers and challenges such as complex technical language, small font size, and time constraints impacted the depth of label engagement and were seen as major hindrances. Nonetheless, label reading was positively associated with greater nutritional public awareness and support for clearer food labelling policies. The findings underscore the necessity for simplified, consumer-friendly labels and early age-appropriate nutrition education. Improving understanding, basic knowledge and accessibility can empower young adults to make more informed, health-conscious food choices.

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